

EXECUTIVE INFLUENCE AND INVESTIGATIVE INTERDEPENDENCE: USE AND MISUSE OF CENTRAL AGENCIES AGAINST CORRUPTION CASES

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ABSTRACT

The Central Agencies(CAs) became a tool of political harassment by the ruling regime against opposition members, the press, etc., to suppress voices raising against the government. The problem lies in the formation, working and functioning of these Agencies. The authors find merit in the statement made by Justice R M Lodha about unfavourable impression of the CAs in general perception, especially CBI, that it is “caged parrot speaking in master's voice”, discuss various cases to reach the conclusion that CAs are indeed misused by all ruling governments from time to time to secure their political objectives. It also identifies the unwillingness of the ruling Government to let this parrot fly from its cage, and its willingness to train and empower this parrot to speak in its voice to settle its political score. And for that purpose, the government has continuously flouted every judicial directive and direction given by the Courts, and recommendations given by various commissions and committees. The CAs thus emerged as a threat to the federal structure of India and a tool to intimidate and harass the State Government, which has a different Party government from the Centre. This Paper is explanatory in nature and tries to identify the problems associated with the working and functioning of CAs, especially CBI, CVC and ED, the control exercised by the government on them and the possible misuse of these Agencies by the government authorities, specifically in corruption cases. It explores the possible solutions of this problem.

Keywords – Corruption, Central Investigating Agencies, CVC, CBI, ED.

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I. INTRODUCTION

As per the preamble of the Constitution, India is a '*sovereign, Socialist, secular, democratic republic*' and It is a union of states¹. It has a federal structure with unitary features². The parliament is authorised to make law for the entire country, while the legislature of the state is authorised to make law for the entire state³. Where the executive power of Parliament extends to make law regarding any matters exclusively provided in the List I⁴, and it enjoys federal supremacy over the matters enumerated in the State list i.e., list II and Concurrent list i.e., list III of the seventh Schedule⁵. The executive power of the State extends to ensure that it complies with the law made by the parliament and the existing laws of the state, and the Parliament extends to giving such directions to the state as it appears the GOI necessary for that purpose⁶. Thus, Government's prime function is to protect the State, and the government for that purpose employs various machineries and agencies to protect the state from all kinds of threats and to maintain peace, law and order in the state. Under the Constitution of India, Public Order and Police fall under Entry 1 and 2 of State list(List II) of the VIIth Schedule respectively, thus laws with regard to these subjects are to be made by the States. But, the Government of India deploys police and military to maintain peace, law and order in the society and protect the state, and certain agencies are conferred with the power to investigate, which helps these states ensure the state's security⁷. The Entries 8 and 80 of the Union List (List I) of the VIIth Schedule, which falls exclusively in the domain of the Central Government, talks about the Central Bureau of Intelligence and Investigation, and about police force belonging to any state and the extension of powers and jurisdiction of members of such police force, with consent of such state, respectively.

Thus, to deal with the exigencies, both internal and external, which could affect the integrity, sovereignty, security, and peace of the Country, the Parliament from time to time, created various Central Agencies, For Example- Research and Analysis Wing (R&AW), Central Bureau of Investigation(CBI), Intelligence Bureau(IB), Narcotics Control Bureau (NCB),

¹ Constitution of India, 1950, art. 1

² Governance & Administer, available at: <https://www.india.gov.in/topics/governance-administration> (last visited on 10 September 2025)

³ Constitution of India, 1950, art. 245

⁴ Constitution of India, 1950, art. 246(1)

⁵ State of West Bengal v. Committee for protection of Democratic Rights, West Bengal, AIR 2010 SC 1467

⁶ Constitution of India, 1950, art. 256

⁷ Chiranthana N Yadav, "A Study on the Central Investigating Agencies in India and the FBI in the USA" 3 Indian Journal of Law and Legal Research 1(2021-22)

National Investigating Agency(NIA), Director of Revenue Intelligence (DRI), etc. These intelligence and investigative agencies of India are responsible for countering all activities which are detrimental and prejudicial to the interest, sovereignty, and security of India⁸, to combat the menace of corruption and maintain transparency in the system. These Central Investigative and Intelligence Agencies work in addition to and sometimes independently of the State police to maintain both internal and external security of India. But, these Central Agencies, especially Central Investigative Agencies, are often criticised by the people, civil society, opposition and various stakeholders for being the puppet of the Central government and severely damaging the federal structure character of the Indian polity. It is alleged that these agencies are used by the Centre for its political benefit. These allegations are not completely baseless and are backed by facts and numbers, we will discuss forthwith.

The need for Central Agencies to deal with Corruption cases

The Secretary General of the United Nations, during the adoption of the UN Convention against Corruption, give a broader view on the corruption around the world, observing its detrimental impact on the economy of a country and diverting funds from welfare measures and misdirecting the government's attention from welfare to contain corruption, he further added that it not only effect the economy but, '*undermine democracy and rule of law, leads to violation of human rights*' and give an environment to flourish crimes such as terrorism, organised crimes, etc.⁹

Corruption is the abuse of power by a person who has been conferred such power, for personal benifits, it "erodes trust, weakens democracy, hampers economic development and further increases inequality and poverty, widened social division and the environmental crisis"¹⁰. It has far-reaching implications not only on the economy of the Country but also on the entire system of governance. Corruption is a bug that slowly hollows out the entire system of the country. So, it is very important to curb this menace of corruption.

⁸ Central Intelligence and Investigative Agencies of India, *avaliable at:* <https://lotusarise.com/central-intelligence-and-investigative-agencies-of-india-upsc/> (last visited on 8 September 2025)

⁹ Speeches, *avaliable at:* https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/about-unodc/speeches/speech_2003-10-31_1.html (last visited on 8 September 2025)

¹⁰ What is Corruption?, *avaliable at:* <https://www.transparency.org/en/what-is-corruption> (last visited on 8 September 2025)

Score of India in the Corruption Perception Index of Transparency International (out of 100)		
Year	Score out of 100	Rank out of 180 countries
2022	40	85
2023	39	93
2024	38	96

Thus, as per 2024 Corruption Perception Index of Transparency International, India ranked 98 out of 180 countries with a score of 38 out of 100, the score has dropped by one point lower than in 2023¹¹. The performance of India is dropping from year to year, it shows that corruption is on rise in India.

There are various reasons for corruption in India, such as weak law and law-enforcement agencies, monopoly, and lack of transparency and accountability¹². Corruption has a detrimental effect on the entire system of the Country. It increases poverty and inequality, affects the healthcare and education system, erodes public trust, increases political instability, reduces transparency and weakens democracy¹³

There are multiple agencies, to deal with corruption, which is considered the genesis of all other menaces in society. The Central Government has created various Centralized Agencies to combat corruption, and these agencies play a pivotal role in dealing with corruption in India. These Central Agencies are tasked to conduct investigations and gather evidence. Subsequently, the Court places reliance on such gathered evidence and gives judicial decisions¹⁴. Centralisation of the Anti-Corruption Agency helps the government and gives it a high hand in the fight against corruption, however, cooperation and coordination of other bodies are also necessary¹⁵. But, the government is constantly working to keep all the powers to control and regulate the Central Investigative Agencies within itself exclusively, and though these agencies have some success in resolving complex cases like corruption that threaten peace, security and integrity of the country. And it continuously flouted all the judicial

¹¹ Corruption Perceptions Index, available at: <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2024> (last visited on 8 September 2025)

¹² Anti-Corruption Enforcement Mechanisms Framework in India, available at: <https://share.google/mWs7NNYfGKglp8fr> (last visited on 11 September 2025)

¹³ *Ibid*

¹⁴ Utkarsh Mishra and Sanchita Singh, "Examining the need for Standard Operating Procedure in light of criminal investigation by Law Enforcement Agencies" 4 Indian Journal of Law & Legal Research 1 (2022)

¹⁵ Centralised versus decentralised anti-corruption institutions, available at: <https://share.google/eE3BwYaSBZt86UTFw> (last visited 8 September 2025)

directives and directions given by the Apex Court, and recommendations given by various commissions and committees *per contra* to such objectives of the government.

Central Agencies: Powers and functions to combat corruption

To identify whether the Government uses or misuses the Central Agencies in corruption cases, it is very important to discuss some of the Central Agencies, which work exclusively to combat corruption in India. Below, the authors discuss various Central Agencies, their power and function to combat corruption:-

A. Central Vigilance Commission (CVC):

The GOI to examine corruption in various government departments, constituted the Santhanam Committee, which recommended various measures to check corruption in government departments. The Committee recommended to establish a Central Vigilance Commission and to confer it with the power to inquire and investigate corruption matters, where a Public servant of the Central Government is involved¹⁶ especially for the offences related to the Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 1988. It will not be subordinate to any ministry or department and enjoy the same autonomy and independence as the Union Public Service Commission, and shall exercise superintendence over the functioning of the CBI (under DPSEA) in so far as it relates to the investigation of offences under the Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 1988¹⁷. It shall consist of a Central Vigilance Commissioner and two Vigilance Commissioners¹⁸. The members of the commission or the Commissioner shall be chosen amongst a panel of Civil servants, who have knowledge and experience in matters relating to vigilance, policy making and administration or a person who is holding office in a corporation under the Central government, having expertise and experience in finance¹⁹. The Secretary is to be appointed by the Central Government²⁰. Its functions include to exercise superintendence over and giving directions to the Delhi Special Police Establishment and review the progress of investigation, inquiring into or investigating any case referred to it by the Central Government, or any complaint which

¹⁶ The Central Vigilance Commission and the Central Bureau of Investigation: A brief history of some developments, available at: <https://share.google/xzxXYmuDzN6zkdZMp> (last visited on 12 September 2025)

¹⁷ *Ibid*

¹⁸ Central Vigilance Commission, 2003, s 3(2).

¹⁹ Central Vigilance Commission, 2003, s. 3(3).

²⁰ Central Vigilance Commission, 2003, s. 3(4).

is made against any officials specified in Section 8(2) involving any employee of the Central Government, for commission of an offence under PMLA, 1988 or under CrPC, or charged for a similar trial²¹. However, prior approval of the Central Government is required in cases where the offence alleged under the PMLA is committed by an employee above the Joint Secretary level, appointed by the Central government and by officers of the corporation, where such corporation comes under the direct control of the Central Government²².

B. Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI):

The CBI draws its power from the Delhi Special Police Establishment Act, 1946, and originated as the Special Police Establishment (SPE) established by the government in the year 1941 to deal with corruption that emerged during WWII purchases²³. CBI was brought through a resolution²⁴. CBI earlier used to come under the Home Department, but on the recommendation of the Santhanam Committee, it was transferred to the Ministry of Personnel, Pension & Public Grievances and works under the superintendence of the CVC in respect of offences alleged to be committed under PMLA²⁵. There is thus a system of dual control over the CBI, on one hand it under control of CVC, only with respect to corruption cases but, even if related to corruption the CVC's superintendence over CBI's work is restricted to offences alleged against an official specified in Section 8(2) involving any employee of the Central Government, who has committed an offence under PMLA, 1988 or under CrPC, charged for a similar trial and on the other hand under the central government in respect of its other work²⁶. Thus, CBI, which was initially formed to deal with corruption over a period, gained prominence and became a premier investigating police agency in India²⁷. As per the object and reason of the DSPE Act, 1946, DSPE was brought to deal with certain

²¹ Central Vigilance Commission, 2003, s. 8(1).

²² Central Vigilance Commission, 2003, s. 6A.

²³ FAQ, available at: <https://cbi.gov.in/faq#:~:text=During%20the%20period%20of%20World,4> (last visited on 12 September 2025)

²⁴ Resolution No. 4/31/G1 dated 11 April 1963

²⁵ Central Bureau of Investigation, Powers, Functions, CBI vs State Police, available at: <https://vajiramandravi.com/upsc-exam/central-bureau-of-investigation/#:~:text=In%201963%2C%20the%20CBI%20was,specialized%20works%20are%20discussed%20below> (last visited on 12 September 2025)

²⁶ *Supra* note 16

²⁷ Central Bureau of Investigation, available at: <https://cbi.gov.in/about-us?search=what-we-do#:~:text=The%20Central%20Bureau%20of%20Investigation,investigating%20police%20agency%20in%20India> (last visited on 10 September 2025)

offences in the Union Territory of Delhi, but it is not confined merely to union territories, and with the consent of the state governments, its jurisdiction has been extended to all states across India as per section 6 of the DPSE Act, 1946²⁸. It can take a case if²⁹: (i) the concerned state government requests for an investigation by it, and the central government agrees to such a request, (ii) State has issues a notice u/s 6 DSPE Act, 1946 giving its consent to CBI to investigate cases in the State, subsequently such consent of the state is notified by the Central Government u/s 5 of the DSPE Act, and (iii) on the order of the High Court and Supreme Court. The CBI thus does not have absolute jurisdiction to investigate cases of the state³⁰ and it can be done only with the consent of the Central and State governments or on the order of the Supreme Court or High Courts. The High Court of a state can direct CBI to take up a case even without the consent of the concerned state in exercise of its power under Article 226 of the Constitution³¹. Entry 8 of List I, i.e., State List of the VIIth Schedule of the Constitution of India, provides for “Central Bureau of Intelligence and Investigation”. It has all the powers and privileges available to the police force³². It has three divisions- (i) Anti-Corruption Division, to deal with corruption cases against central government employee, under the Prevention of Corruption Act, 1988 and Prevention of Corruption (Amendment) Act, 2018, (ii) Economic Offences Division, to deal with all types of economic offences such as fake currency, fraud cases and cyber crimes and (iii) Special Crime Division, to deal with serious and organised crimes³³.

C. Enforcement Directorate (ED):

ED is a multi-disciplinary organisation which investigates offences related to finance, specifically under the Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002, the Fugitive Economic Offenders Act, 2018(FOE) and the Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999(FEMA)³⁴. The object and reason of PMLA provides that the Act, 2000 is brought

²⁸ Delhi Special Police Establishment Act, 1946, s. 6

²⁹ <https://cbi.gov.in/faq>

³⁰ <https://share.google/xzxXYmuDzN6zkdZMp>

³¹ State of West Bengal & Ors. Vs. Committee for Protection of Democratic Rights, West Bengal & Ors. (2010) 3 SCC 571,

³² Management of Advance Insurance Co. Ltd. Vs. Gurudasmal, (1970) 1 SCC 633.

³³ Can CBI take over the investigation of a criminal case registered by the state police, *available at*: <https://cbi.gov.in/faq> (last visited on 13 September 2025)

³⁴ *What we do, available at*: <https://enforcementdirectorate.gov.in/#:~:text=What%20we%20do,foreign%20exchange%20market%20in%20India> (last visited on 14 September 2025)

for the '*prevention of money laundering and for the confiscation of property derived from it*'. The ED is empowered to investigate the cases involving money laundering, trace assets derived from proceeds of crime, attach property, which is the proceeds of crime³⁵, confiscate such property and secure the prosecution of offenders³⁶. According to the object and reason of the Act, FEMA aims to promote '*the orderly development and maintenance of the foreign exchange market in India*'. ED under this Act is empowered to investigate any act in contravention of section 13 of the Act, and conduct search and seizure³⁷ both within and outside India³⁸. It is authorised to conduct an investigation and conduct a search & seizure even if there is a suspected contravention of the provision³⁹. ED under this Act has similar powers as the Income Tax Authority, which are conferred upon the authorities under the Income-Tax Act, 1961⁴⁰. Under the FEO Act, 2018, the ED is empowered to attach the property of Fugitive Economic Offenders, who are declared fugitive and provide for confiscation of their property⁴¹

II. Executive Influence and Investigative Independence on the Central Agencies

The Central Agencies are often criticised and questioned for being under excessive executive influence and for a lack of investigative independence. The Central Government exercises exclusive and unbridled control over the Central Agencies, their functioning and working and thus, it is often used as a tool to suppress political dissent and opposition. The government is constantly working to keep all the powers to control and regulate the CAs with itself, and though it has some success in resolving complex cases like corruption can threaten the economic security, and safety and security of the country, the government make every attempt to keep these agencies under its control. An uncontrolled power and influence exercised by the Central Government over these agencies, and the government does not want to loose control over these agencies, and it can be inferred from the fact that, after so many years, CBI, which is the most prominent investigating agency in India, lacked proper statutory backing and, the rules and regulations are not clear and are subject to the notification of the Central Government from time to time. Till now, no law has been enacted to govern the working and functioning of

³⁵ Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002, s. 5

³⁶ *Supra note 34*

³⁷ Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999, s. 37(1)

³⁸ Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999, s. 37A

³⁹ *Supra note 34*

⁴⁰ Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999, s. 37(3)

⁴¹ *Supra note 34*

CBI. The influence on CAs can also be inferred from the statement of Justice R M Lodha⁴² about unfavourable impression of the CAs, especially CBI, that it is “caged parrot speaking in master's voice” the statement identifies the unwillingness of the Government to let this parrot fly from its cage, and the underlying willingness to train this parrot to speak in its voice for its political interest and this is the main reason for the ineffectiveness of the CAs. It further identifies that the government is constantly working to keep all the powers to control and regulate the CAs with itself, and though it also has some success in resolving complex cases like corruption that threaten the peace of the country, the government has made every attempt to keep these agencies in its control.

2.1.1. On the recommendation of the Santhanam Committee, the GOI in the year 1964 established the Central Vigilance Commission, specifically to deal with corruption cases where Public servants are involved, this step of the government was widely appreciated. But, when the infamous Hawala case⁴³ came the real state of the art of Central Agencies, came before the Supreme Court and presented grim reality of the existing system of these agencies and their working came into light, the Court gave various direction for CVC & CBI related to ED and its independence, and recommended a Nodal agencies of different Investigative agencies to work together for effective and efficient functioning of there agencies. It also criticises the single directives⁴⁴. The Court further observed that the directions issued by it under Article 32 r/w 142 will be implemented as the rule of law under Article 141 of the Constitution and thus, be binding⁴⁵. In an attempt to nullify the Supreme Court's judgment in the Hawala case, the Government of India attempted to bring a more favourable vigilance law. The GOI formed the Law Commission to bring a Report on CVC in the year 1998, and while the report was still awaited, the government subsequently called a Cabinet Committee Meeting, which prepared a draft of the CVC Bill. The Government then promulgated the CVC Ordinance, 1998 on 25th August 1998 as per the draft prepared by the Cabinet Secretary⁴⁶. The Ordinance was brought as an attempt to override the judgment of the SC in the Hawala case. The Ordinance was criticised widely, and as a result, on 27th October 1998, the government introduced the CVC(Amendment)

⁴² *Manohar Lal Sharma v. The Principal Secretary and others*, 2014 (3) SCC 163

⁴³ *Vineet Narain v. Union of India*, (1998) 1 SCC 226

⁴⁴ *Vineet Narain v. Union of India*, (1998) 1 SCC 226 para 47

⁴⁵ *Vineet Narain v. Union of India*, (1998) 1 SCC 22 para 53

⁴⁶ *Supra note* 16

Ordinance, 1998. Government of India then introduced the CVC Bill, 1998 but it lapsed. The CVC Bill, 1999, was brought and subsequently passed by the Parliament and became the CVC Act, 2003, but this Act still retains some of the provisions, which SC criticised in the Hawala case, such as the provision of a single directive, the qualification of the members and the commissioner⁴⁷.

From time to time, CBI is also criticised, and it was recognised by the Courts, civil society and even by the general public. And though, indeed, the control over CBI does not mean control over the investigation of CBI directly, but such a notion would not water down the administrative control and supervision over the Central government⁴⁸ and the control exclusively exercised by the government over CBI calls to question the partiality, independence and transparency of CBI. After so many directions issued by the Court on various occasions, with regard to granting extension to the tenure of ED and CBI director⁴⁹, there is a continuous attempt by the government to grant extension to them⁵⁰.

2.1.2 The Central Agencies, CBI, ED, etc., do not have their own investigating machinery, and they rely to a greater extent on the state police and need their cooperation and coordination for its working and functioning. The police are generally criticised for being under political influence and considered as a tool to harass the general public and curb dissent, the general public, thus, is unwilling to trust the State Police⁵¹. But the point is that Central Agencies like CBI are equally prone to misuse and impacted by political influence, and even their chance of being influenced and misused by the central government is greater.

The question thus arises as to why central agencies like CBI, ED, etc., have gained prominence over state police for so many years, even after they suffer from defects such as executive influence and investigative inter-dependence. The answer lies in the ill reputation of the state police in the eyes of the general public. The fact that Central

⁴⁷ Writ Petitions (Criminal) Nos. 340, of the -343 of 1993.

⁴⁸ *State of West Bengal v UOI*

⁴⁹ Vineet Narain(1997) and Alok Verma(2018)

⁵⁰ CBI/ED Tenure Extension Day #1: Dr. Singhvi Explains Threat to Independence of ED, *available at: <https://www.scobserver.in/reports/cbi-ed-tenure-extension-1-dr-singhvi-argues-that-tenure-extensions-hamper-independence-of-ed/>* (last visited on 14 September 2025)

⁵¹ *Supra note* 16 at 18

agencies, unlike State police, are remote from the scene, are considered impartial and cannot be easily manipulated and influenced by Local politics and thus, considered to perform impartial and independent investigation⁵².

But, despite so many administrative, legislative and political setups at all levels, corruption still persists in India⁵³ with different scams coming into light daily, it not only affects individuals but the whole system altogether.

III. Use and Misuse of Central Agencies by the Government and its Impact on federal Structure

As mentioned earlier, efforts, measures, rules, regulations, and laws were put forward by the Government at all levels to tackle the growing issue of corruption in India, the Central Investigating Agencies are at the centre of the fight against corruption and play a very crucial role in this fight. They work to combat corruption to advance transparency and fairness in the system. ED has secured an overall 92 % conviction during the last 5 years⁵⁴ and 94% conviction rate in PMLA cases in the year 2024 alone⁵⁵. It also recovered assets worth over 34,000 Rs during the year 2024⁵⁶. The conviction rate of CBI in the year 2022 is 74.59%⁵⁷. Thus, there is a good record of CBI in prosecuting high-profile corruption cases. Similarly, the effectiveness of ED in seizing proceeds of crime and assets derived from such proceeds of crime in money laundering cases, despite these agencies being criticised for being affected by politics, lack of independence, delayed and lengthy investigations⁵⁸ so what goes wrong?

As observed by Dr B. R. Ambedkar, “However good a Constitution may be, it is sure to turn out bad because those who are called to work it happen to be bad”. Similarly, happens in the

⁵² *Supra* note 16 at 18

⁵³ *Supra* note 16

⁵⁴ ED's conviction rate in PMLA cases over 92% in last 5 years: Official data, available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/india/eds-conviction-rate-in-pmla-cases-over-92-in-last-5-years-official-data/articleshow/123169480.cms?from=mdr> (last visited on 14 September 2025)

⁵⁵ ED says it has secured over 94% conviction rate in PMLA cases, available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/ed-says-it-has-secured-over-94-conviction-rate-in-pmla-cases/article70053035.ece> (last visited on 15 September 2025)

⁵⁶ ED says it has secured over 94% conviction rate in PMLA cases, available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/ed-says-it-has-secured-over-94-conviction-rate-in-pmla-cases/article70053035.ece> (last visited on 14 September 2025)

⁵⁷ Government of India, available at: <https://sansad.in/getFile/annex/259/AU3962.pdf?source=pqars> (last visited on 16 September 2025)

⁵⁸ Nikhil Tiwari and Ambar Srivastava, “Role of Special Investigation Agencies in criminal justice system: A comparative study with the India, U.K. and U.S.A” 6 Indian Journal of Research Publication and Reviews 75-83 (2025)

cases of law and regulations, however good the laws and regulations are, if the enforcement is bad and the enforcing agency is working malafide, such laws and regulations will be bad. Thus, in case of laws and regulations related to Central Agencies, the laws are good and effective, but its misuse by the government and such misuse can not be denied, e.g., as of 31.01.2023, 513 persons were arrested by ED and only 45 accused were convicted by the Court⁵⁹. Political interference, post-retirement posting of officers of central agencies, shortage of manpower and resources, outside the scope of RTI⁶⁰ make central agencies prone to being misused. There is also concern regarding the violation of human rights⁶¹, and personal liberty during the functioning and working of these agencies, for example, former CJI D. Y. Chandrachud talked about instances of seizure of personal devices during raids conducted by the Central Investigative Agency and recognised the need to strike a balance between investigative right of the agency and individual privacy and liberty⁶². The SC has also, in various cases, expressed its concern over the low conviction rate under PMLA, where the rate of conviction is less than the complaints registered and arrests made⁶³. Thus, it can be said that the Central Government exercise greater control over the functioning and working of the CBI.

These abuses of the CAs by the government have a far-reaching impact, it is not restricted to impacting the life and liberty of the individuals but has the potential to impact the autonomy and independence of the States and its governments, thus, it poses a possible threat to the overall Federal Structure of India. In *State of West Bengal v UOI*⁶⁴ case, the State of WB filed a suit against the Central government for advancing investigation by CBI, even after WB had withdrawn the consent for CBI probe, the Court rejected the argument raised by the Central Government that CBI is an independent statutory body, and thus, the Central Government cannot be sued, and held that the CBI function under the control of Central Government and thus, the suite against the Central government is maintainable.

⁵⁹ Key details of PMLA cases up to 31.01.2023, available at: <https://enforcementdirectorate.gov.in/statistics-0> (last visited on 16 September 2025)

⁶⁰ Central Bureau of Investigation, Powers, Functions, CBI vs State Police, available at: <https://vajiramandravi.com/upsc-exam/central-bureau-of-investigation/> (last visited on 16 September 2025)

⁶¹ *Supra note 59*

⁶² Important to 'pick our battles', probe agencies should concentrate on crimes that threaten security, economic health of nation: CJI, available at: https://www.ptinews.com/stories-detail/national/Important-to--pick-our-battles---probe-agencies-should-concentrate-on-crimes-that-threaten-security--econolicense_cancelledmic-health-of-nation--CJI/1398487/1 (last visited on 16 September 2025)

⁶³ Supreme Court questions 'poor' conviction rate in ED cases, available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/supreme-court-questions-poor-conviction-rate-in-ed-cases/article69907025.ece> (last visited on 16 September 2025)

⁶⁴ *State of West bengal v UOI*

There are various instances where the Government misused the Central Investigative agencies for political purposes, and such misuse is not only restricted to the members of opposition, but extends to NGOs, Civil Societies, Environmentalists, press, etc., and this trend not only impacts citizens but, poses a serious threat to the federal structure of the Indian polity. Some of the instances, where the working and functioning of CAs came into question are as follows:-

- During the year 2023-24 alone, the Government of India cancelled the license of more than 100 NGOs, among which are included some prominent NGOs, like Rajiv Gandhi Charitable Trust, Oxfam India, Rajiv Gandhi Foundation, Centre for Policy Research,⁶⁵ raid was conducted by the Income Tax department on the offices of these NGOs, and the move was criticised around the world and perceived as a blow to the right to freedom of speech and expression, and association⁶⁶. But such a move is not new, and the ruling government has been taking these measures to curtail dissent. For example, the government has cancelled the FCRA licence of 20,701 NGOs since 1976⁶⁷. Though there were some lapses on the part of the organisation, the stringent action taken by the government is more influenced by political motives.
- The dilly-dallying working and functioning of the CBI in dealing with various scams further erodes the public trust. There are many other cases involving corruption since Independence till now such as Jeep scandal (1948), the Mundra deals (1957-58), the Malaviya-Sirajuddin scandal (1963) and the Pratap Singh Kairon case (1963), Bofors Scam(2002), the Mudgal case (1951), Bihar Fodder Scam, Jain Diaries(Hawala case), Sahara scam(2014), Punjab and Maharashtra bank crises(2019), Vijay Malya, Nirav Modi and Mehul Choksi loan fraud, which shows the CAs inefficiency and effectiveness to combat corruption in India. The SC also, in various cases, criticised the working and functioning of these agencies.

⁶⁵ Why 20,701 NGOs lost their FCRA licences since 1976: Cause, impact decoded, *available at:* https://www.business-standard.com/finance/personal-finance/why-20-701-ngos-lost-their-fcra-licences-since-1976-cause-impact-decoded-124041200227_1.html (last visited on 17 September 2025)

⁶⁶ India: Authorities must stop weaponizing central agencies to clamp down on civil society, *available at:* <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2022/09/india-authorities-must-stop-weaponizing-central-agencies-to-clamp-down-on-civil-society/> (last visited on 15 September 2025)

⁶⁷ *Supra note 66*

- During the years 2015-2020, eight states have withdrawn their general consent granted to CBI under Section 6 of the DSPE Act, 1946⁶⁸ barring CBI-led investigations in their respective states. Telangana and Tamil Nadu have also withdrawn their consent in 2023⁶⁹ and Karnataka in 2024⁷⁰, the majority of these states are ruled by parties that are in opposition at the Centre. This situation reveals the underlying insecurity of the States to accept the investigative jurisdiction of the Central Investigating Agencies, especially the CBI, because of the possible threat of it being used by the Central government. Fourteen opposition parties moved to the Supreme Court against the Central Government, alleging misuse of the Central Investigative Agencies, CBI, and ED by the Central Government. Misuse of Central agencies by alleging corruption charges on opposition leaders has the potential to impact the federal structure of India, and raise question on its integrity of the CBI functioning. The recent cases of arrest of the setting chief ministers of various states in corruption charges raises a serious question on the motive of CAs. Many opposition leaders, including former Delhi Chief Minister Arvind Kejriwal, Deputy Chief Minister Manish Sisodia and former Jharkhand Chief Minister Hemant Soren, were arrested in alleged money-laundering cases.

Data collected by the Indian Express in the year 2022, '*from court records*', showed 400% jump in cases registered by ED since 2014, mainly against the opposition party⁷¹. The use of Central Agencies by the Central Government to intimidate its political opponent is a serious threat to the federal structure of India. There are instances where corruption charges are levied against the political opponent, but when they joined the ruling government, all charges were dropped against them. These types of practice have a detrimental effect on the federal structure of India.

⁶⁸ States Barring CBI Investigation, available at: <https://www.pib.gov.in/Pressreleaseshare.aspx?PRID=1707269> (last visited on 18 September 2025)

⁶⁹ 10 states withdraw general consent to CBI to investigate cases: Centre, available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/india/10-states-withdraw-general-consent-to-cbi-to-investigate-cases-centre/articleshow/106151348.cms?from=mdr> (last visited on 19 September)

⁷⁰ As Karnataka withdraws general consent to CBI, which other states have taken this route, available at: <https://indianexpress.com/article/political-pulse/cbi-karnataka-general-consent-withdrawal-other-states-9590450/> (last visited on 20 September 2025)

⁷¹ Is ED the new CBI? Data shows 400 per cent jump in political leaders under agency scanner, majority from Opposition, available at: <https://www.financialexpress.com/india-news/is-ed-the-new-cbi-data-shows-400-per-cent-jump-in-political-leaders-under-agency-scanner-majority-from-opposition/2681531/> (last visited on 21 September 2025)

IV. Role played by the Courts in containing the unbridled power of the Central Agencies

The CAs' working and functioning are criticised by the Courts in various cases, the due, fair and just exercise of power by these agencies is very important to ensure the rights of the citizen. In the infamous Bofors Scam⁷² case, the Single Judge Bench of Justice R.S. Sodhi of the Delhi High Court raised suspicion on the working and functioning of CBI, and observed that “CBI has been under a cloud. It has been accused of being a political shield or a whip of the government of the day”. In another case, the Jharkhand High Court criticised CBI and observed that “it has failed to live up to its reputation”⁷³. To ensure an impartial, fair, and just investigation by the CAs, it is very important to eliminate any kind of political influence over these agencies. The High Courts and the Supreme Court from time to time have given various orders, directions and directives to keep in check the working and functioning of CIAs, Some of the important directions given by the Court are as follows:-

- **No prior approval of the government, in case of Public Servants:** In the case of *Subramanian Swamy vs. Director, CBI*⁷⁴, the Supreme Court held that section 6A of the DSPE Act is violative of Article 14 of the Constitution and declared, Section 6A of the Delhi Special Police Establishment Act as unconstitutional, which requires prior approval of the government in case of investigation is conducted against civil servants. The SC discouraged the practice of prior approval of the Government in cases involving senior civil servants under the Central Government.
- **Keep the CAs away from the government interference:** In the case of *Vineet Narain v Union of India*⁷⁵ popularly known as the Jain Hawala case, the Supreme Court has given various directives to freed agencies like CBI and ED from the Union's political interference. The unjust, unfair, inequitable, and arbitrary working and functioning of the CBI came into light in the case of *Vineet Narain*. The Supreme Court admitted that the Central Government exercises wide power and control over the working and functioning of CBI and ED, and gave directives to the Government to be implemented for making CBI and ED independent and free from the control of the Central government. But, the continuously, flouted all the directions of the Supreme Court keeps finding a back door.

⁷² *Prakash P. Hinduja v. Union of India*, 2002 SCC OnLine Del 679

⁷³ *State of Jharkhand v. Lalu Prasad Yadav*

⁷⁴ *Subramanian Swamy v. CBI*, (2014) 8 SCC 682

⁷⁵ *Vineet Narain v. Union of India*, (1998) 1 SCC 226

- **Liability of Judges under PMLA:** In the case *K. Veeraswami vs. UOI*⁷⁶, the question came before the consideration as to whether High Court and Supreme Court Judges will be held liable under PMLA. The SC answered in the affirmative and held that though the Act applies to Supreme and High Court Judges, but held that a criminal case cannot be registered against Judges without obtaining the assent of the Chief Justice of India.
- **Arrest must be made in compliance with section 19 PMLA:** In the case of *Pankaj Bansal v. Union of India*⁷⁷ the Supreme Court held that the ED is conferred with the duty to curb corruption in India, and for that matter, it must exercise its power in a fair, reasonable and transparent manner and held that a mere order of remand is not sufficient. The arrest of a person under PMLA must be made in conformity with section 19 of the Act, and any act in contravention of it shall be illegal and will be violative of Article 22(1) of the Constitution.
- **Bail to certain category of persons under section 45 PMLA:** *K Kavitha*, BSR legislator, was lodged in Tihar jail in the Delhi Excise Policy case since April 2024⁷⁸. The Supreme Court set aside the order of the High Court rejecting the bail application of Kavitha under the proviso to section 45(1) PMLA and observed that the High Court was wrong in giving the observation that she “cannot be equated to a vulnerable woman”⁷⁹. The Supreme Court thus, gave her the benefit of the proviso to section 45(1) PMLA and granted bail.
- **‘Bail is a rule and jail is an exception’:** The Supreme Court in the *Manish Sisodia's case*⁸⁰, observed that the prolonged jail or detention of a person to custody before he is convicted is a pre-trial punishment and reiterated that bail is a rule and jail is an exception.
- **Order of Investigation of cases by High Court and Supreme Court:** The Supreme Court in the case of *State of West Bengal vs. The Committee for Protection of Democratic Rights, West Bengal*⁸¹, held that the High Court under Article 226 and Supreme Court under Article 32 of the Constitution can order the CBI to investigate a case, in absence of consent due to withdrawal of consent or otherwise of the State government under section 6 of the DSPE, but such power must be exercised by the Court cautiously. But, in no case the Central government alone authorise CBI to investigate a case in a State, if the State has withdrawn its consent.

⁷⁶ *K. Veeraswami v. Union of India*, (1991) 3 SCC 655

⁷⁷ *Pankaj Bansal v. Union of India*, (2024) 7 SCC 576

⁷⁸ Delhi excise policy case | CBI arrests BRS legislator Kavitha, available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/cbi-arrests-brs-legislator-kavitha-in-delhi-excise-policy-case/article68053555.ece> (last visited on 25 September 2025)

⁷⁹ *Kalvakuntla Kavitha v. Enforcement Directorate*, 2024 SCC OnLine SC 2269

⁸⁰ *Manish Sisodia v. Enforcement Directorate*, (2024) 12 SCC 660

⁸¹ *State of W.B. v. Committee for Protection of Democratic Rights*, (2010) 3 SCC 571

From time and again, the Supreme Court of India and various High Courts gave decisions to advance fairness and transparency in the working and functioning of CAs. The Courts recognised the need to balance the fair investigation and life and liberty of citizens, so CAs must not be used as a political tool to suppress political dissent.

V. Conclusion

The Executive Influence and Investigative Interdependence exercised by the government has a detrimental effect on these Central Agencies it not only prejudices the interest of the citizens but, puts the entire system of governance at peril. IT erodes public trust, is detrimental to the economic health of the country and prejudicial to democratic values. The Government enjoy wide power over these Agencies, which makes it prone to misuse. But, the usefulness and effectiveness of these agencies must also not be doubted because over the years, these Agencies took several measures with the help of the Government to combat corruption. Corruption is a worldwide phenomenon, and no nation-state in the world is untouched by it. Justice Dipak Mishra⁸² termed corruption as “national economic terror” and a “social calamity”, and recognised the need for special laws to deal with it. Thus, the administrative or executive influence of the Government over these Agencies is not an issue on the contrary, sometimes it is necessary because it enjoys wide power, and the Central Government works as a watchdog and keeps a check on such power of the Central Agency. Thus, the real problem lies in the apprehension of these Agencies being misused by the Union Government for political purposes. The instances of Setting Chief Ministers being charged with corruption case, though there could be merit in each case, the possible involvement political motive cannot be completely discarded. The fear of the States of its possible misuse and apprehension of harassment by the Union Government forced many states to withdraw their consent. The road is long to make these Agencies more empowered and independent, but what is the need of the hour is that the Union Government show some political maturity and aid these agencies in their fair, impartial and just functioning to eliminate the menace of corruption from the Indian society. And strictly implement the directions given by the various committees, commissions and directions given by Supreme Court and various High Courts.

⁸² *Yogendra Kumar Jaiswal v. State of Bihar*, (2016) 3 SCC 183